

Parametric Studies for Establishing a Neutronics-Thermal-Hydraulic Design Space for High Performance Fast Spectrum Chloride Based Molten Salt Reactors

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ABSTRACT

Molten salt reactors were first demonstrated in the 1950s and continue to attract significant attention due to their numerous advantages over conventional light water systems. These benefits include increased operating temperature, atmospheric pressure in the primary loop, and online refueling capabilities just to name a few. Additional benefits such as breeding and waste burning can be obtained with fast spectrum MSRs. Traditional fast spectrum MSRs rely on chloride salts due to their favorable neutronic performance. However, chloride-based salts can be potentially mixed with FLiBe-based salts to enhance their thermal hydraulic performance. There are, however, many pros and cons in using various salts' mixtures that can only be understood using proper modeling and simulation to account for the neutronic performance within the fuel cycle, thermal-hydraulics, and chemical compatibility. This work is only the first step in developing a computational framework that will allow for the comparison of different salts. More specifically, in this work parametric studies are performed over various chloride salts to determine the thermal-hydraulic and neutronics tradeoffs associated with specific chloride salt compositions. Simple neutronics parameters including the leakage fraction and fission to capture ratio are compared across various salts. These same salt compositions are then fed in a coupled neutronics-thermal hydraulics where parameters such as pumping power and flow velocity are compared. The results show that $MgCl_2$ is a poor performer in all metrics, KCl is superior neutronically, and that $LiCl$ has the best thermal-hydraulic performance.

Keywords: molten salts, fast reactor, thermal-hydraulics, parametric studies,

1. INTRODUCTION

The Generation IV international Forum, in its efforts to help develop advanced reactor designs, have identified six "revolutionary designs" categorized as generation IV due to their advanced operational and safety features. Of these generation IV designs one of the most promising is the molten salt reactor (MSR). MSRs are desirable for their passive safety, high outlet temperature, online refueling capability and low operating pressure. MSRs operating with a fast spectrum bring the additional benefits of breeding and waste burning. Although the concept of MSRs has been around since the 1950s only three examples have operated, none of which were commercial reactors. Holcomb, D.E et al (2011) explored both fluoride and chloride salt systems from a fuel cycle perspective and concluded that fluorides perform better in thermal systems and chlorides perform better in fast systems [1]. Studies regarding the French molten salt fast reactor (MSFR) design concluded that fluoride cores require less volume than their chloride counterparts [2]. Kasam, A. et al (2020) performed thermal-hydraulic trade off studies

for their breed and burn molten salt reactor (BBMSR) design by examining many parameters, such as power density, temperature rise and pumping penalty, and their relation to the fuel salt volume fraction [3]. The same thermal hydraulic framework was later used to analyze the coupled effects with fuel utilization, level of fuel enrichment, and internal core geometry [4]. TerraPower's MCFR has also undergone preliminary neutronic and thermal-hydraulic analysis where fuel salt flow rates, pressure drops, critical core volume, and reflector cooling were of prime importance [5].

In addition to the neutronic and thermal considerations mentioned above, it is well understood that fuel composition has a strong impact on the behavior of the reactor, i.e., fuel cycle effects or thermal performance via the variation in thermophysical properties variation. The objective of this work is to perform coupled neutronics- thermal-hydraulic analysis on a range of fuel salt compositions to establish a design space for fast spectrum MSR. Both fluoride and chloride based MSRs have been investigated neutronically and thermal-hydraulically for fast and thermal systems. This work represents only a subcomponent of a larger project to produce a complete design for a high performance fast MSR, which must have the following characteristics:

- **High Power Density:** A smaller physical footprint will lead to more modular construction and reduced cost.
- **Breed & Burn capabilities:** A reactor that can maintain a high conversion ratio will require less fuel over its operational lifetime.
- **High Outlet Temperature:** A high outlet temperature not only allows for greater thermodynamic efficiency but also allows for the reactor to generate high quality process heat for industrial processes.

The fuel salt composition must allow for a high conversion ratio as well as a high fission rate and must maintain a strongly negative temperature feedback coefficient. On top of this, the salt should have good heat transfer properties; a fuel salt may be capable of maintaining an exceeding large power density, however this becomes irrelevant if that heat cannot be removed. These design objectives impose stiff requirements on the possible fuel salt compositions. Fluoride based salts will have more desirable thermal-hydraulic performance; however, they will also produce a softer neutron spectrum and negatively impact the breeding capability of the reactor [1,2,5]. Obtaining the optimal salt composition means considering all possible options. Studies done on the MCFR and BBMSR designs limit themselves to a single binary or tertiary salt system, whereas this work considers four different chloride salt systems with the objective of narrowing the chloride fuel salt design space.

2. METHODOLOGY

The results presented in the following section were obtained from a coupled thermal hydraulic model using the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC and the in-house developed reduced order heat solver CoRE-ThM [6]. Coupled solutions were obtained using the following procedure:

1. First the core is discretized, with the total core power divided evenly between all layers to generate a uniform power profile
2. This uniform power profile is fed into the thermal-hydraulic solver which will obtain the axial temperature and density distribution.
3. The temperature distribution is then passed back to OpenMC. During this step, both the temperature and thermophysical properties of the salt are updated.
4. Using the new temperature distribution OpenMC will obtain the axial power distribution and pass it back into the solver.
5. This iterative procedure repeats until the relative error in temperature in each layer is less than 0.1%.

Thermophysical properties of the fuel salt were updated using data from ORNL's molten salt thermal database (MSTDB) [7]. All fuel salts analyzed in this work were tertiary mixtures. The properties of each mixture were obtained from its unitary components using ideal mixing rules. The properties of interest are density, viscosity, thermal conductivity, and specific heat capacity as shown in Eqs. 1 through 4 respectively.

$$\rho_{mix} = \frac{\sum_i x_i m_i}{\sum_i x_i V_i} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

$$\nu_{mix} = \sum_i x_i \ln \nu_i \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$k_{mix} = \sum_i x_i k_i \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

$$c_{p_{mix}} = \sum_i x_i c_{p_i} \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

Where x_i is the molar fraction of component i and V_i is the molar volume of component i

Most neutronics parameters of interest, such as the fission to capture ratio and leakage fraction, were acquired directly from the OpenMC tallies. Thermal fuel feedback coefficients were determined by plotting the core's reactivity as a function of temperature and obtaining the slope. The average energy of neutrons causing fission was calculated using the method described in the MCNP user manual [8].

$$\bar{E}_f = \frac{\sum_g \frac{E_g - E_{g-1}}{2} \nu \Sigma_{fg} \phi_g}{\sum_g \nu \Sigma_{fg} \phi_g} \quad \text{Eq.5}$$

Where E_g and E_{g-1} are the upper and lower bounds of the energy group, ν is the number of neutrons produced per fission, Σ_f is the fission cross section and Φ_g is the neutron flux in energy group g .

The thermal-hydraulic parameters of interest were obtained using 1-D axial solution from the heat solver. One of the more important metrics was the pumping power required for the fuel salt to flow through the active core. The allowable temperature rise through the core as well as total core power were fixed quantities across all cases. To obtain the pumping power, first the mass flow rate had to be obtained by iterating on the mass flow rate until the prescribed temperature rise across the core was satisfied. Once this mass flow is obtained, the pumping power can be calculated using equation 6. The total pressure drop across the core was taken to be a sum of gravity losses, acceleration losses, and friction losses.

$$P_{pump} = \Delta P Q \quad \text{Eq.6}$$

CoRE-ThM allows the user to specify specific heat transfer and friction factor correlations. For this study the Churchill equation was used for the friction factor:

$$f = 8 \left[\left(\frac{8}{Re} \right)^{12} + \frac{1}{(A+B)^{1.5}} \right]^{\frac{1}{12}} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$A = \left[2.457 \ln \left(\frac{1}{\left(\frac{7}{Re} \right)^{0.9}} \right) \right]^{16} ; B = \frac{37530}{Re}$$

And the Gnielinski correlation was used for the heat transfer coefficient.

$$h = \frac{k}{D} \left(\frac{\mu_b}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.11} \frac{Re - 1000Pr f_m^{0.125}}{1 + 12.7 (Pr^{\frac{2}{3}} - 1) \left(\frac{f_m}{4} \right)^{0.5}} \quad \text{Eq.8}$$

$$f_m = (1.8 \times \log Re - 1.64)^{-2}$$

2.1. Model Parameters

The core is modeled as a homogenous cylinder. The core dimensions were chosen such that the active core volume would be 12 m^3 . This core volume allows for high power output while maintaining a small physical footprint. The inlet and outlet temperatures as well as total core power are also presented in Table I below.

Table I. Summary of the physical parameters used in the model

Core Diameter	2.54794 m
Core Height	2.35359 m
Inner wall	Hastelloy N (3 cm thick)
Reflector	Magnesium Oxide (40 cm thick)
Outer wall	316 Stainless Steel (3 cm thick)
Inlet Temperature	1000 K
Outlet Temperature	1200 K
Thermal Power	4200 MW
Wall Roughness	$1.51 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}$

Another challenge present in chloride systems is the high capture cross section of ^{35}Cl which is present with nearly 75% abundance in natural chlorine. To combat this, the ^{37}Cl isotope may be enriched. All salt compositions used a chlorine enrichment of 99%.

3. RESULTS

The results presented were obtained using 24 different salt compositions using four different carrier salts. Given that this design is to be a breed and burn reactor, both a fertile and fissile component will be required. The fertile component was chosen to be a natural uranium salt of the form UCl_3 whereas the fissile driver is a reactor grade plutonium (PuCl_3). The reactor grade plutonium vector is shown below in Table II.

Table II. Reactor grade plutonium vector used for the model [9]

Isotope	Atom Fraction
Pu^{238}	3.118 %
Pu^{239}	52.525 %
Pu^{240}	24.121 %
Pu^{241}	12.543 %
Pu^{242}	7.618 %

The mol fraction of carrier salt was adjusted between 10 and 60% for the four candidate carrier salts namely: NaCl , MgCl_2 , LiCl , and KCl . The remaining fraction of the fuel salt was balanced with a mixture of UCl_3 and PuCl_3 where the mol ratio between uranium and plutonium is held constant at 6:1 for all salt compositions.

3.1. Neutronic Parameters

The most general and simple neutronic results to obtain are the eigenvalue, leakage fraction and

fission to capture ratio. For all cases, similar trends were observed: increased fractions of carrier salt result in diminished neutronics performance. Figure 1 shows that while all salts follow the same trends, the difference in key neutronics parameters is not negligible.

Figure 1. Simple neutronic parameters of interest

Overall MgCl₂ appears to be the worst candidate neutronically. It performed the worst in both reactivity, fission to capture ratio and resulted in a leaky core. Despite resulting in the leakiest core, the KCl salt had the highest fission to capture ratio as well as the second highest eigenvalue. The NaCl salt appears to have the best balance of neutronics parameters. The LiCl salt yielded the core with the lowest leakage and favorable fission to capture ratio, but with poor reactivity like the magnesium salt.

Figure 2. Derived neutronic parameters

As a breed and burn reactor, the neutron spectrum is critical. A harder spectrum can yield more favorable cross sections for breeding, therefore the harder the spectrum the better. To compare the spectrum for different cases, we will use the average energy of neutrons causing fission. Figure 2a

shows that increasing the fraction of LiCl and MgCl₂ had negligible effects on the spectrum whereas the NaCl and KCl cases vary significantly based upon the mol fraction present. KCl clearly produces the fastest spectrum, approaching 1.12 Mev when the mol fraction is 60%. When the fraction of NaCl reaches 60%, the average fission neutron energy reaches only 975 kev. The feedback coefficients calculated also present some interesting behavior. The NaCl salts temperature feedback coefficient was relatively independent of the fraction of carrier salt present. In Figure 2b it is shown that KCl salts not only had the most negative feedback coefficient but showed that this value will become more negative as the KCl fraction is increased. Although still strongly negative the MgCl₂ and LiCl salts showed an increase in their feedback coefficients as more carrier salt was added.

3.2. Thermal Hydraulic Parameters

Unlike neutronics studies, identifying a carrier salt with the most favorable thermal-hydraulic properties is simpler. For all the examined cases, the pumping power is low considering the thermal power being generated. While mass flow rates are significantly higher than that of a LWR, they are on par with other chloride systems such as the MCFR [5]. LiCl outperforms all other salts in every comparison. The LiCl salt yields the lowest pumping power, mass flow rate, and core outlet velocity. Both the MgCl₂ and KCl performed poorly in all regards with the MgCl₂ salt being dead last in nearly every metric. The NaCl salt performed far better than either KCl or MgCl₂ but still failed to perform as well as the LiCl salt particularly for the intermediate range of carrier salt fractions.

Analyzing Figure 3 shows that both the pumping power and mass flow rate curves decay exponentially with carrier salt fraction except for LiCl which flattens at around 40 mol % implying that little to no additional power savings can be had by further increasing the LiCl fraction. A similar behavior is observed with the core outlet velocity. The exit velocity of all salts exponentially decays as their mol fraction increases until a minimal value is reached. LiCl reaches its lowest outlet velocity at a mol fraction of 40% whereas the other carriers reach their minimum outlet velocity at a mol fraction of 45-50%. This behavior is due to the rate of change in a salts density vs its specific heat. All compositions experience an increase in specific heat with temperature while the density is exponential. The point of minimum velocity represents the point where the decrease in density begins outpacing the increase in specific heat.

a. Pumping power through the active core

b. Fuel salt mass flow rate

Figure 3. Thermal-hydraulic parameters of interest

3.3. Rankings and Recommendations

Overall, it was determined that KCl is the optimal carrier salt from a purely neutronic standpoint while LiCl is optimal from a purely thermal-hydraulic standpoint. LiCl was ranked lower than NaCl because of the additional complications that can arise from introducing lithium. Anytime lithium is exposed to a neutron flux it will produce tritium through (n, α) reactions.

Tritium imposes several challenges for MSRs due to its tendency to form corrosive compounds such as gaseous HCl and its ability to diffuse through solid boundaries at high temperatures [5]. Many fluorine-based designs mitigate this issue by enriching the ${}^7\text{Li}$ isotope. This is impractical for chloride systems since most designs already enrich the ${}^{37}\text{Cl}$ isotope. The cross section of lithium's (n, α) reaction is decreased greatly at fast energies except for a strong peak around 200 Kev [10]. Depletion studies will need to be performed to quantify tritium production due to having LiCl in the system.

For tertiary systems (systems using three salt components) NaCl is the recommended carrier because of its adequate performance in both studies. For higher order salt systems, additional benefits may be had from a mix of candidate salts. The most attractive option appears to be a mix of LiCl and KCl. Such a mixture would allow for an exceptionally hard spectrum while reducing the leakage fraction and improving the thermal-hydraulic performance of a pure KCl system. Based solely upon the results of this study, MgCl₂ was determined to be a poor carrier salt candidate for fast chloride designs.

4. SUMMARY & FUTURE WORK

Despite the challenges present in fast spectrum reactors, MSRs are one of the most promising advanced reactor designs. The work presented here focuses specifically on the high-performance variant of MSR, having strict requirements for both neutronics and thermal-hydraulic behavior. Salt mixtures common in literature were compared using a coupled neutronic- thermal-hydraulic framework. The results presented will assist with narrowing the design space for future design work in designing fast chloride systems. The primary objective of this study was to capture the trends and tradeoffs between different salt compositions. The results presented, although useful, are not complete. The weakest link in this model is in the thermophysical properties of the salt mixtures. Ideal mixing rules yield only a rough estimate of the actual mixture properties.

The next steps for the high performance MSR project are to develop thermophysical models that better capture reality using non-ideal mixing terms. Another concern is the thermal limits of the reactor vessel, more specifically the wall temperature. Future studies will investigate vessel cooling requirements and

account for them into this coupled framework. Another feature that will need to be added is a model that accounts for the kinetic losses associated with the outflow of delayed neutron precursors from the core. Once these tasks are completed, the neutronic-thermal-hydraulic framework could be coupled to a thermochemical model which will then allow for spatially resolved depletion-driven thermochemistry analysis (SRDDTA) to be performed. Only then will a truly complete MSR design space be obtainable

REFERENCES

1. D.E. Holcomb et al., "Fast Spectrum Molten Salt Reactor Options", *ORNL/TM-2011/105* (July 2011)
2. M.A. Nasr et al., "Neutronic and fuel cycle performance analysis of fluoride and chloride fuels in Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR)", *Nuclear Engineering and Design* (November 2023)
3. A. Kasam et al., "Thermal-hydraulic design methodology and trade-off studies for a dual-salt breed-and-burn molten salt reactor", *Nuclear Engineering and Design* (April 2020)
4. A. Kasam et al., "Neutronic and thermal-hydraulic fuel design for a dual-salt breed-and-burn molten salt reactor" *Nuclear Engineering and Design* (February 2021)
5. Z.Mausloff et al., "Design and Assessment of a Molten Chloride Fast Reactor", *Nuclear Engineering and Design* (August 2021)
6. J. Monaghan, D. Kotlyar. "Extended fuel cycle sensitivity studies of the GE BWRX-300 Design," Global/Top Fuel 2025, October 5-9, Nashville, TN.
7. N.Termini et al., "An Overview of the Molten Salt Thermal Properties Database–Thermophysical, Version 2.1.1 (MSTDB-TP v.2.1.1)", *ORNL/TM–2023/2955* (July 2023)
8. Kulesza, Joel Aaron, "MCNP code version 6.3.0 Theory User Manual", 2022
9. B.Hombourger, "Breed-and-burn fuel cycle in molten salt reactors", *Nuclear Sciences & Technologies* (August 2019)
10. D.A. Brown, M.B. Chadwick, R. Capote, et al., "ENDF/B-VIII.0: The 8th Major Release of the Nuclear Reaction Data Library with CIELO-project Cross Sections, New Standards and Thermal Scattering Data", *Nuclear Data Sheets*, 148: pp. 1-142 (2018).